
AVHRR Curation Project - Keeping 40 years of European AVHRR-LAC data alive

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The year 2022 was one of the hottest for many regions of the Earth resulting in droughts with shortened vegetation periods, exceptional glacier melt, reduced snow cover, strong warming of lakes, rivers and the Mediterranean Sea and many more considerable anomalies of essential climate variables (ECVs) around the globe. Accurate monitoring of these changes relies on long-term time series. Only data from the Advanced Very High-Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) onboard many NOAA- and, since 2006, EUMETSAT MetOp-satellites can provide the necessary length for time series based on an almost unchanged sensor of the last 40 years with daily availability and 1.1 km spatial resolution. This long period fulfils the requirements of the World Meteorological Organization for a statistically sound analysis to study climate change induced shifts of Essential Climate Variables (ECV).

Besides the central NOAA CLASS archive, many local archives exist which are partly not accessible or the data holdings are not adequately maintained to be used by research teams. A few archives in Europe have data holdings covering Europe on a daily basis but are not homogenized and consolidated. In the frame of ESA's Heritage Space programme the data holdings of University of Bern (Switzerland), European Space Agency and Dundee Satellite Receiving Station (UK) are combined, reprocessed and validated to proof readability of the AVHRR LAC level 1b data. Furthermore, a data rescue mission for SHARP formatted data sets received at different European ESA stations was accomplished with a success rate of > 99%. In a final step, metafiles and quick-looks are generated to be included in a data container (EO-SIP). The metafiles include some quality indicators to guarantee the usability of the data set. This may help the user to select the needed files for their own investigations. Finally, the homogenised data set was transferred to ESA to keep the unique AVHRR images alive for the next +50 years and make it accessible for all interested parties via ESA web interfaces. The whole process for consolidation of the AVHRR data was in-line with the recommendations of the CEOS Working Group on Information Systems and Services (WGISS) to fulfil the needs for data management and stewardship maturity. Work is ongoing to generate level 1c data and include the global 1 km data received before the year 2000.

The paper will give some details about the consolidation process to build one of the largest AVHRR archives in Europe, which are a valuable resource for retrieving ECVs. The second part will show some examples of ECVs for a time period of almost 40 years to highlight the value of this exceptional data set.

Keywords: AVHRR, ECV, Third Party Missions; Data Preservation; LTDP Processes; Lifecycle; Data Valorisation, Earth Observation, Heritage Space Programme, Long Time Data Series, Fundamental Climate Data Record

Background

Before the launch of the first AVHRR instrument, the VHRR was its precursor and was in orbit for some years. However, the quality that is required for long term monitoring was not sufficient for the VHRR and only partly achievable by AVHRR. The first AVHRR sensor was a four channel radiometer with a duplication of thermal channel 4. It was onboard of the TIROS-N satellite, which was launched in 1978. An improved version with two thermal channels (AVHRR/2) was carried on NOAA-7 (launched 1981) and continued in subsequent satellites until NOAA-14 (tables 1 and 2). The two thermal channels result in better retrieval accuracy of surface temperatures when the split-window technique is applied. With the launch of NOAA-15, the next generation of AVHRR sensors was installed. AVHRR/3 now has two

channels in the SWIR spectrum (3A and 3B, tables 1 and 2) to improve cloud-snow discrimination. Both channels are automatically switched on the boundary between daylight and night data, since simultaneous operation is not possible. It is remarkable that an old and not particularly sophisticated sensor is now onboard the EUMETSAT Metop series and keeping the system operational until 2025. Within the framework of the Joint Polar Satellite Systems (JPSS), an agreement between NOAA, NASA and EUMETSAT included the decision to deliver three of the AVHRR sensors (manufactured by ITT Exelis, Indiana) to be mounted on Metop-satellites to continue the generation of unique time series until the end of their planned service period, which is expected for 2025 or some years later. In the end, more than 40 years of daily Earth observations will be available for long term studies to support climate change research activities. The “health” of these satellites is continually monitored and the data is publicly available on the Polar Orbiting Environmental Satellites (POES) web page (<http://www.ospo.noaa.gov/Operations/POES/status.html>).

AVHRR Dataset Curation Project

The main objective of the ESA Heritage Space Programme is to guarantee the preservation of the data from all EO ESA and Third Parties ESA managed missions in the long term, also ensuring their accessibility and usability, as part of a joint and cooperative approach in Europe aimed at preserving the EO European data from member states’ missions. The need to ensure the preservation of the Earth Observation data has been expressed by practically all environmental monitoring programmes and recently again through Climate Change related initiatives. There is a strong need for a homogenous data set covering at least Europe for the last 30 years as it was pointed out by different user groups. The AVHRR sensor on-board of NOAA- and EUMETSAT MetOp-satellites is the only system providing global data with a daily and medium spatial resolution over the last four decades. University of Bern (Switzerland) is receiving the AVHRR data stream since the year 2000 and has archived data covering whole Europe from 1989 until 2022 including other archives. Only a few data gaps caused by problems with the receiving antenna. However, additional data exist at ESA facilities and other centres to fill the temporal and spatial gaps. Of particular interest are data from 1981 until 1989 to expand the time series to the past that has been offered from the Dundee University. Independently of these and other gaps, a unique data record was compiled due to the almost unchanged configuration of the AVHRR sensor. Hence, the final goal of the project was to provide a public accessible AVHRR data set covering Europe for a time span of more than 40 years. Due to the fact that the available AVHRR data sets archived at UniBern, ESA and other external sources cover different regions and times a consolidation was needed. The following figure 1 shows the amount of the AVHRR core data set archived at University of Bern. Furthermore, the ESA AVHRR dataset has been included in this project. The format of the different archived data from these sources differs and a specific processor is needed to homogenise all these products and the available different input product level. This approach ensures the starting point of higher product level production.

Figure 1: FDR AVHRR HRPT / level 1b data archive at University of Bern.

The AVHRR Data Set Curation Project covered the following main objectives:

1. Generate an AVHRR European Master Data Set (Level-0 and Level-1) based on the harmonisation and combination of the ESA and University of Bern (UniBern) AVHRR Data Set

holdings (“Core Data Set”), complemented in gaps with data from other agencies and organisations;

2. Assess benefit to supplement the AVHRR European Master Data Set with the alignment of the worldwide data set collected in the frame of the “1Km” Project carrying out a technical feasibility analysis of the reprocessing effort and cost;
3. Consolidate the preserved data set composition for the AVHRR European Master Data Set and collect or generate the relevant information and documentation with relevant metadata as a complement to the AVHRR Data Records;
4. Validate the AVHRR European Master Data Set reprocessing baseline and reprocessed Data Sets with data experts; Data Set promotion and outreach related activities.

AVHRR Consolidation process

The AVHRR data archive of University of Bern was defined as the master data set for the AVHRR curation project in the frame of ESAs Heritage Space Programme. The data set is mainly composed of AVHRR data in HRPT format and level 1b format, both following NOAA convention. Other products in L1a, L1b formats are available too.

Figure 2: ESA final consolidated L1b products.

From the initial UniBern and ESA data gap analysis and due to some gaps in the time-series, additional AVHRR data was included from other sources, mainly from Dundee University.

The EO product data collected and compiled from the holdings of UniBern-RSGB (1989-2020), ESA (1982-2012), and the Dundee Satellite Receiving Station (1981-1988) represented the data source of the project, available as Level 0 scenes (with few exceptions), albeit not in a single, homogeneous format. They provide the basis for the Level 0 AVHRR European Master Data Set and the generation of the Level 1A and Level 1B Master Datasets. The decision for the final formats was supported by the AVHRR advisory group, a team of international experts with in-depth knowledge in AVHRR processing. Following the described consolidation procedure, the AVHRR data from different sources were re-processed for the L1b homogenisation. In addition, quality information was extracted and included in the L1B metadata file of each product. Finally, the consolidated master data set was packed in EO-SIP format to be archived at ESA facilities.

In detail, after the generation of the consolidated and detailed inventory lists describing the data holdings of the RSGB and ESA AVHRR archives and together with the actual AVHRR scenes and derived metadata the procedure created the AVHRR Level 0 Master Data Set. The next iteration covered the generation of the Level 1A Master Data Set from the Level 0 data and thus the preparatory steps to convert the AVHRR data to the NOAA Level 1B format. The final step of the project was the production of the L1B files and subsequently the Level 1B Master Dataset.

The figures below present an overview of the reprocessing procedure.

Fig.1: Reprocessing Procedure – Overview.
Based on inventories of the different archives the AVHRR Level 0 Master Data Set is generated. Afterwards Level 1A and 1B are processed.

Figure 3: Consolidation schema.

The Level 1A Master Dataset provided all the information necessary for a successful conversion of the data into the NOAA AVHRR Level 1B format. The workflow to generate L1B EO-SIPs includes the steps:

- unpack the EO-SIP product data from the L1A Master Dataset
- get both the metadata needed for the EO-SIP file names and the data conversion into the NOAA AVHRR Level 1B format from the L1A Master Data Set
- build the base file names from the metadata
- convert the data into the NOAA AVHRR L1B Format
- create a browse image from AVHRR channel 2 (day) or 4 (night)
- derive / complement the EO-SIP metadata
- generate the EO-SIP quality report
- build the L1B EO-SIP product data tarball
- combine the tarball, browse image, metadata, quality report in a L1B EO-SIP.

The data conversion from the intermediate L1A EO-SIP to the L1B format is usually done in a single tool which:

- unpacks the L0 data stream; the sensor data come as 10 bit values, 3 of them are packed into 4 byte words during the conversion
- includes the metadata with the time information, orbit number, attitude data
- adds the calibration data for the visible channels and mission specific constants (platinum resistance thermometer weighting and polynomials, equivalent widths, integrated solar irradiances and effective central wavelengths for the visible channels, space radiances, normalized response functions, and non-linearity correction factors for the thermal channels)
- adds the grid coordinates from the TLE entry associated with the scene
- adds the solar and viewing geometry from the TLE entry associated with the scene.

Fig.4: workflow Level 1B
The workflow visualizes the steps to extract all needed information and transfer Level 1B data into EO-SIP container.

Figure 4: Consolidation procedure from L0 to L1b.

Figure 4 shows the nominal workflow, although sometimes the L0 was missing from the initial inputs, hence the available L1a was used as the processor input to create the corresponding L1b. Furthermore, there was an additional case in which just the L1b product was available (no L0 or L1a) and the processor processed the input to produce the homogenised L1b product.

Global Land 1 km-AVHRR project in '90s

In the past, scientific investigations indicated that significant global earth science information can be derived from the 1 kilometre (km) Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) image data acquired by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration's (NOAA's) TIROS polar-orbiting satellite program. During the early 1990's, various groups, including the International Geosphere-Biosphere Programme (IGBP), the Commission of the European Communities (CEC), the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectrometer (MODIS) Science Team, and others have identified the need for the acquisition and compilation of a global 1-km resolution multi-temporal AVHRR data set. NASA identified this data set as critical to the preparatory studies for the Earth Observing System (EOS). As a result, NASA Headquarters asked the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS), EDC Data Center (EDC) to coordinate the preparation of such a data set as a part of its role as the EOSDIS/Land Processes Distributed Active Archive Center.

Based upon current AVHRR data collection efforts by NOAA, the USGS, the European Space Agency (ESA), Australia's Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation (CSIRO), and a number of non-U.S. AVHRR receiving stations, it appeared feasible to collect a global land 1-km AVHRR

data set over all land surfaces using NOAA's TIROS "afternoon" polar-orbiting satellite. This effort, therefore, required a great deal of international cooperation to ensure the acquisition and compilation of the data set. Further, the project required full endorsement from the Committee on Earth Observing Systems (CEOS) Plenary, through the recommendation of the CEOS Working Group on Data (CEOS-WGD), for the compilation of the data set. CEOS Plenary endorsement facilitates international cooperation in ensuring participation and completion of the data set. The strategy of acquisition was tailored to four major participants, namely NOAA, with its High Resolution Picture Transmission (HRPT) stations and the Local Area Coverage (LAC) recorder; ESA, with its AVHRR HRPT ground station network; and the USGS and NASA, with the USGS/EDC AVHRR HRPT ground station network augmented by key CSIRO/Australian HRPT stations, cooperate to assume responsibility for the acquisition and compilation of a global land 1-km AVHRR data set. Figure 5 gives an overview of the contributing HRPT receiving stations.

On the 1st of April 1992, the project officially began with 23 stations worldwide plus the NOAA local area coverage (LAC) on-board recorders capturing, copying, and transferring the 1-km data to the EDC. Initially the data were to be collected continuously for 18 consecutive months continuing through the 30th of September 1993; subsequently the period was officially extended to the 30th September 1996 with a second extension until the end of 1999.

This global AVHRR data set in 1-km spatial resolution, received from ESA stations is archived at ESA facilities. This data set is available as NOAA level 1b file in EO-SIP with all included meta-files and quality indicators. In this ESA dataset, the data acquired over the European region is not included, being in the next data collection.

Figure 5: ESA and USGSS acquisition stations.

European 1-km AVHRR data collection

The European continent is very well covered due to the wide swath of AVHRR sensor (2.700km) and the distributed receiving stations located in Europe. University of Bern has coverage from the North Cape to Northern Africa, Free University of Berlin reception was able to cover an area even further north and to the East. Whereas the station located at Dundee covers more the western area including the North Atlantic. All ESA stations cover the whole of Europe from the far north (station Tromsø) to the southern tip of Europe (station Maspalomas).

More than 260.000 AVHRR data sets are now archived at ESA and available for the users in L1b format. The consolidated and harmonised data set covers the years 1981 – 2020. The following figure gives an overview of the archived datasets.

Figure 6: European 1-km AVHRR archive hosted at ESA.

In addition to this European coverage and the global 1km land AVHRR (1992 - 1999) dataset, valuable data sets are archived with high value for ECV retrievals. For this reason, ESA is collecting and retrieving the following regional data archives:

- Canada – CCRS / CCMEQ
- Australia – CSIRO
- China – CMA
- Mongolia – Ulaanbatar
- Brazil – INPE
- Argentina - GiDyC-Servicio Meteorológico Nacional
- South Africa – SANSA
- Central Africa – Kenia (ASI and University of Rome)

Once the datasets of Africa and South America have been received, the idea is to process them to regenerate the L1b product.

Essential Climate Variable (ECV)

It is worthwhile to focus on remote sensing in climatology, as progress in this field has been very well documented by the IPCC in the last Assessment Reports. Not only is there an increased likelihood of man-made changes documented, the increasing contribution of satellite remote sensing for the monitoring of global conditions are of particular importance to the work. The retrieval of essential climate variables (ECVs), defined by Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) with satellite data has now been proven as a viable, complementary source of information along with the use of ground measurements and climate model results. Many parameters can be monitored with satellite sensors, and to some extent, with an impressive degree of accuracy. However, this is only valid for the latest missions with good sensor calibration and stability. These data sets are a valuable contribution to monitor the changes on Earth and the atmosphere, but most systems in orbit have a short life time of approximately 5-10 years. The World Meteorological Organization (WMO) reported that a time series of at least 30 years is needed to retrieve statistically significant changes of ECVs. Considering that these are extended periods of time, only a limited selection of satellites and sensors can be used for global monitoring – one of these is the Advanced Very High Resolution Sensor (AVHRR) onboard of NOAA satellites (since 1978) and on the EUMETSAT platform Metop (since 2006).

The Essential Climate Variables	
Domain	Essential Climate Variables
Atmospheric (over land, sea and ice)	Surface: Air temperature, precipitation, air pressure, surface radiation budget, wind speed and direction, water vapour.
	Upper air: Earth radiation budget (including solar irradiance), upper air temperature (including MSU radiances), wind speed and direction, water vapour, cloud properties.
	Composition: Carbon dioxide, methane, ozone, other long-lived greenhouse gases, aerosol properties.
Oceanic	Surface: Sea surface temperature, sea surface salinity, sea level, sea state, sea ice, currents, ocean colour (for biological activity), carbon dioxide partial pressure.
	Sub-surface: Temperature, salinity, currents, nutrients, carbon, ocean tracers, phytoplankton.
Terrestrial	River discharge, water use, ground water, lake levels, snow cover, glaciers and ice caps, permafrost and seasonally-frozen ground, albedo, land cover (including vegetation type), fraction of absorbed photosynthetically active radiation (fAPAR), leaf area index (LAI), biomass, fire disturbance, soil moisture.

Figure 7: Essential Climate Variables defined by GCOS.

Data sets from AVHRR sensor can contribute significantly to these listed ECVs.

ECV examples

The section shows only a few examples of essential climate variables retrieved from the long time series of AVHRR. Further information showing more examples and studies is available at: https://www.geography.unibe.ch/research/remote_sensing_group/publications/index_eng.html. It is worth noting that the previous described AVHRR level 1b data are the starting point for the investigations, however a pre-processing is essential for further usage of the data. This includes calibration of the channels 1, 2 and 3a and an improvement of calibration for the thermal channels. Furthermore, geocoding (incl. orthorectification) is applied to guarantee a precise knowledge of pixels positions for the 40 years time-series. After the successful pre-processing the AVHRR data set can be used to develop procedures to retrieve ECVs.

Snow cover

Due to changes of the climate with increased warming and shifted precipitation regimes, the snow cover reflects these changes. Snow plays an important role in our environment, reflecting more than 80% of the incoming solar radiation back to space, insulating permafrost areas and act as a water storage during winter time releasing melt water during spring/ early summer. The unique long time series of the AVHRR sensor can contribute to measure the changes and its variability during the last 40 years. The following figure shows an example of the European Alps (Hüsler et al. 2014) highlighting the annual cycle but also the strong variability from year to year. The 1-km spatial resolution is sufficient to study changes in large catchments, regions and different altitudinal levels, respectively. The coverage of the wide AVHRR swath in combination with a daily resolution makes the sensor also an ideal source for country or continental studies.

Figure 8: Snow covered area of the European Alps derived from AVHRR data set. Hüsler, F., T.Jonas, M.Riffler, J.P.Musial, S. Wunderle (2014): A satellite-based snow cover climatology (1985 -2011) for the European Alps derived from AVHRR data. The Cryosphere, 8, 73-90

Lake Surface Water Temperature (LSWT)

Lake surface water temperature (LSWT) is an important parameter with which to assess aquatic ecosystems and to study the lake's response to climate change. The AVHRR archive of the University of Bern offers great potential to derive consistent LSWT data suited for the study of climate change and lake dynamics. To derive such a dataset, challenges such as orbit drift correction, non-water pixel detection, and homogenization had to be solved. The result is a dataset covering over 3.5 decades of spatial LSWT data for 26 European lakes. The validation against in-situ temperature data at 19 locations showed an uncertainty between ± 0.8 K and ± 2.0 K (standard deviation), depending on locations of the lakes. The long-term robustness of the dataset was confirmed by comparing in-situ and satellite derived temperature trends, which showed no significant difference. The final trend analysis showed significant LSWT warming trends at all locations (0.2 K/decade to 0.8 K/decade).

Figure 9: Retrieval of Lake Surface Water Temperature based on AVHRR data to study the influence of climate change for European Lakes (left) and two anomaly plots for Lake Trichonida (Greece) and Inarijärvi (Finland). More details: Lieberherr, Gian; Wunderle, Stefan (2018). Lake Surface Water Temperature Derived from 35 Years of AVHRR Sensor Data for European Lakes. Remote sensing, 10(7), pp. 1-25. MDPI 10.3390/rs10070990

Conclusion

The European AVHRR Master Dataset is available via ESA standard data access web sites (<https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/missions/noaa>) in L1b format, but very soon the AVHRR L1c will be available to the users. The initial major effort was to rescue the dataset and to consolidate it considering that inputs had different formats and were not necessarily compliant with the NOAA HRPT or L1a format. This required detailed and specific processor development by University of Bern. The production of the homogenised L1b products suffered in specific project step the lack of documentation or the memory of the acquisitions so that the enforce again the ESA Heritage Space Programme objective.

The AVHRR project is now continuing with the production of the first of the AVHRR Level 1C data that is created from the homogenised L1b format. The L1C data will calibrated and geometrically corrected

Figure 10: L1C consolidation process.

Furthermore, ESA is working on the generation of a Fundamental Data Record (FDR) including AVHRR and instruments on board of other satellites considering the different spectral, spatial and radiometric resolution of the sensors. The FDR will provide the measurement uncertainties and implement the FIDUCEO outcomes, too.

As shown in the section of examples, the AVHRR sensor and the compiled time series in the frame of ESA Heritage Mission is a unique and valuable source to generate 40-year time series of ECVs. Independently of available ground measurements or it's accessibility from previous decades, one can now study with good accuracy the changes of our environment focusing on different ECVs as defined by Global Climate Observing System (GCOS). These time series are a valuable source of information for climate modelling user groups (CMUG), regional authorities and many science teams. This underlines the need to keep such a unique data set alive and accessible for the next +50 years.